

Effect of salt and solvents of the BZ reaction system containing tartaric acid and acetone as mixed organic substrate

V. V. Gajre, C. Basavaraja and V. R. Kulkarni*

Department of Studies in Chemistry, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga-585 106, India

E-mail : vijaykumar2@sanchamet.in

Manuscript received 2 August 2003, revised 6 January 2004, accepted 20 February 2004

For the oscillating system containing BrO_3^- - Mn^{II} -tartaric acid and acetone in various acid media, the effects of salts like potassium nitrate and potassium sulfate and a representative non-aqueous solvent soluble in water like 1,4-dioxane have been studied; the oscillatory characteristics have been computed. Mechanistic possibilities for the observed behavior have been suggested.

B-Z Oscillatory reactions have been modified in various ways¹. The oscillations of such systems are supposed to be not only due to instability arising due to autocatalysis, but also due to large differences between the rate constants of some sets of pseudo-elementary reactions. There have been reports of effects of deliberate addition of ethanol, chloride ions, etc. on the behavior of the BZ systems^{2,3}. During our previous studies we had reported the behavior of the BZ systems in various acid media⁴. Addition of salt and solvent provides two other important ways to change the rates of reactions. If we know the nature of oscillations in non-aqueous medium it may be possible to formulate the methodologies to introduce non-aqueous systems. These reasons prompted us to see the effect of salts such as K_2SO_4 , KNO_3 and solvents like 1,4-dioxane on the oscillating system containing BrO_3^- - Mn^{II} - tartaric acid and acetone in various acid media.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 represents the traces of the oscillatory system with indicated initial composition in sulfuric acid media. It can be noted here that the potential of platinum electrode is 250 mV (with respect to SCE) before the addition of bromate. At point A bromate is added; this results in a sudden increase in the potential to about 600 mV (with respect to SCE) up to point B. From B to C there is a relatively slow increase in the potential. This is followed by rapid increase CD. From point D, the potential nearly remains constant for a long time, till point E, where a rapid decrease occurs along EF. At point F there is a slow increase in potential to point G. FG seems to be similar to BC. At G, a rapid increase in potential occurs upto point H. This is followed by a rapid decrease in potential. Thus the point H is similar to

Fig. 1. Platinum electrode traces, composition : $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{tartaric acid}] = 0.06 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 0.002 \text{ M}$, $[\text{acetone}] = 0.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{bromate}] = 0.05 \text{ M}$.

point E. From this point onwards decrease and increase in potential occurs with more or less same amplitude for some time. Oscillations continue for much longer time than indicated in the Figure. The time upto point F can be considered to be the preoscillation period or time of initiation. After this point, the time for each oscillation could be called the time period of oscillations.

If we consider the platinum electrode to indicate the mixed potential, then it can be considered that the more positive side of the potential would indicate the higher concentration of oxidized species namely, Mn^{III} and a lower concentration of bromide. The concentration of Mn^{III} increases and this remains nearly steady during the preoscillation period. After which there is a regular decrease and increase in the concentration of the redox species Mn^{III} as well as bromide

Effect of salts :

The salts chosen for study were potassium nitrate and

Table 1. Effect of K_2SO_4

Concentration Acids	No salt		0.1 M		0.5 M		1 M	
	Time of initiation (s)	Time period (s)						
H_2SO_4	950	150	1050	140	1200	130	1400	110
H_3PO_4	300	850	400	860	450	880	470	900
$HClO_4$	800	250	400	140	650	160	750	200
HNO_3	1150	350	500	360	700	380	900	400

Table 2. Effect of KNO_3

Concentration Acids	No salt		0.1 M		0.5 M		1 M	
	Time of initiation (s)	Time period (s)						
H_2SO_4	950	150	1000	130	1150	120	1300	100
H_3PO_4	300	850	350	820	380	800	460	780
$HClO_4$	800	250	1100	170	1400	165	1800	160
HNO_3	1150	350	1400	320	2060	310	2480	300

potassium sulphate at various concentrations. These studies were done in perchloric acid, nitric acid and phosphoric acid media. Figs. 2 and 3 represent the platinum electrode

Fig. 2. Dependence of oscillatory behavior on the initial $[K_2SO_4]$, composition : $[HClO_4] = 0.5 M$, $[tartaric\ acid] = 0.06 M$, $[Mn^{II}] = 0.0002 M$, $[acetone] = 0.5 M$, $[bromate] = 0.05 M$, $[K_2SO_4]$: (1) nil, (2) 0.1 M, (3) 0.5 M and (4) 1 M.

Fig. 3. Dependence of oscillatory behavior on the initial $[KNO_3]$, other compositions are same as in Fig. 2. $[KNO_3]$: (1) nil, (2) 0.1 M, (3) 0.5 M and (4) 1 M.

traces at different concentrations of potassium sulphate and potassium nitrate respectively, in perchloric acid medium. Tables 1 and 2 represent the salient oscillatory features for the concentrations of these salts in various acid media. The effect of potassium nitrate on the oscillatory characteristics is rather straightforward in all the acid media. When the system with no salt and 0.1 M salt are compared, we observe that the preoscillation period has increased, while the period of oscillation has decreased.

However the effect of potassium sulphate seems to be complicated and is dependent on the acid media :

(1) In sulfuric acid medium the behavior is similar to that of potassium nitrate.

(2) In phosphoric acid medium both the preoscillation period and period of oscillations increase with salt concentration.

(3) In perchloric acid medium when the systems with no salt and with 0.1 M salt are compared, one finds that the preoscillation period as well as the period of oscillation have decreased nearly half. However further increase in salt concentration increases the values of both the parameters.

(4) In nitric acid medium when the system with no salt and with 0.1 M salt are compared one finds that the preoscillation period has decreased nearly half while the period of oscillations shows no such behavior. On the other hand it shows a slight increase. However further increase in salt concentration increases the values of both the parameters.

The FKN mechanism of the BZ reaction can be divided

into four component processes :

(1) Reduction of bromate by bromide to liberate bromine without any involvement of radicals.

(2) Reduction of bromate by the metal catalyst involving autocatalytic step wherein radicals play an important role. It is during this process that the metal is rapidly oxidized.

(3) Removal of bromine by the organics, namely acetone in this case.

(4) The reaction of oxidized metal species with the organics, namely tartaric acid in this case.

The salts may affect the rates of the above reactions either by the ligand capacity of the respective anions and/or by the primary salt effect. In sulfuric acid and phosphoric acid media the ligand effects of the added sulfate may not be important (as sulfate, phosphate are already present in large excess) while in perchloric acid and nitric acid media the complexing abilities of sulfate may be of significance. All other aspects have to be understood in terms of the primary salt effect. The rate constant involving the primary salt effect is⁵

$$\log k = \log k_0 + 1.02 Z_A Z_B \sqrt{\mu} \quad (1)$$

The first two component processes of the FKN mechanism involve either a reaction between two oxybromine species or between bromide and oxybromine species. Here $Z_A Z_B$ can be considered as positive and may be with larger magnitudes depending on the charges. While the last two component processes either involve a reaction between bromine and organic species or between metal and organic species. If these reactions are considered as involving at least one neutral species the above equations do not predict any major salt effect.

The increase in preoscillation period with salt concentration observed in majority of the cases may be rationalized as due to the comparatively slower rates of the last two processes which are responsible for the removal of bromine and the regeneration of the reduced form of the metal ion which are essential for oscillations to occur. After the required intermediates accumulate during this preoscillation period the decrease in the period of oscillations observed in many of the above cases may be rationalized as due possibly to the increase in the rates of the first two component processes. However it is difficult at this stage to rationalize the other complications observed.

Effect of solvent :

Fig. 4 represents the platinum electrode traces at different volume percentage concentrations of 1,4-dioxane

Fig. 4. Dependence of oscillatory behavior on the initial [dioxane], other compositions are same as in Fig. 2. [dioxane] : (1) nil, (2) 2% (3) 4% and (4) 10%.

in sulfuric acid medium, while Table 3 provides the salient oscillatory features for some concentrations in various acid media. It can be observed that the addition of dioxane decreases the preoscillation period, period of oscillations and also the lifetime of oscillations in all the acid media. Further at higher concentrations of dioxane no oscillations are observed. This behavior is similar to the effect observed when the initial temperature of the BZ system in an aqueous solution is increased⁶. Thus it does appear that the rates of the component reactions increase.

The factors usually taken into account while considering the role of solvent are :

- (1) Dielectric constant (d.c),
- (2) Solvation of the reacting particles, and
- (3) The effect of keto-enol equilibrium of the organic substrate.

The dielectric constant of 1,4-dioxane, is rather very low i.e. 2.2. Again 1,4-dioxane is completely soluble in water. A simple theory of two ions interacting in a solution leads to an equation

$$\ln k = \ln k_0 - \frac{(Z_A Z_B e^2)}{d_{AB} E k T} \quad (2)$$

where Z_A and Z_B (positive or negative) indicate the number of charges on the ions, E is the dielectric constant, d_{AB} is the distance of the ions in the activated complex. Thus the rate constant between two oppositely charged ions is more in a nonaqueous medium than in an aqueous medium. It would be expected that some types of oxidation-reduction reactions occur in non-aqueous media as in an aqueous system. However, at the same time, it is found that the oxidizing and reducing ability of a given oxidant or reductant will

Table 3. Effect of dioxane

Concentration	No dioxane		2%		4%		10%	
	Time of initiation (s)	Time period (s)	Time of initiation (s)	Time period (s)	Time of initiation (s)	Time period (s)	Time of initiation (s)	Time period (s)
H ₂ SO ₄	950	150	470	50	320	32	No oscillation	
H ₃ PO ₄	300	850	150	450	100	250	No oscillation	
HClO ₄	800	250	600	100	100	50	No oscillation	
HNO ₃	1150	350	57	100	40	100	No oscillation	

vary from one solvent to another. Thus the magnitude of the oxidation potentials will vary with the solvent, and it is likely that the actual order of potential will change to some extent also.

The degree of solvation of the reactant and the activated complex has a very pronounced influence on the rate of reaction. If the reactants are not appreciably solvated but the activated complex is, the activity coefficient of the complex is smaller and consequently the rate of reaction will be greater. This appears to be the situation in the case of 1,4-dioxane containing systems.

Any solvent that can form hydrogen bonds with the carbonyl group of the keto form will stabilize this form². The enol form, however, since it forms an intramolecular bond will be largely prevented from forming hydrogen bonds with the solvent. Thus the keto form is stabilized with respect to the enol in the BZ system containing no dioxane. When the amount of dioxane increases the enol concentration will tend to become larger resulting in faster rates of reactions. Bromination of the active methylene hydrogen of acetone occurs through electrophilic substitution by Br⁺ ion. The Br⁺ ion will be solvated more in the solvent mixtures containing dioxane, compared to mixtures containing no dioxane. Thus Br⁺ in dioxane mixture will lead to faster bromination leading to a near steady state behavior at higher concentrations of dioxane where no oscillatory behavior is then observed.

The observations reported indicate a complex behavior. An understanding of the behavior appears to be possible in the case of a simple salt like potassium nitrate and also that of the solvent, 1,4-dioxane. A thorough understanding would however require simulation of the behavior with better-understood model⁷. Work in these lines is in progress.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and were dissolved in double-distilled water. Requisite volumes of stock solutions except bromate were placed in the reaction cell⁸ and then the solution in the cell was diluted to 50 ml

inclusive of the last addition of bromate to start the reaction. Smooth bright platinum was employed as indicator electrode and saturated calomel was used as the reference electrode together with 10% KNO₃ as salt-bridge having a sintered disc at the end dipping in the reaction mixture. The platinum electrode was placed in the reaction mixture and the whole experiment was carried out at 30 ± 0.1° with the help of a thermostat. The reaction mixture was stirred with a magnetic stirrer. When the temperature of the reaction mixture became constant (±0.1°), the bromate solution thermostated at the same temperature was instantly transferred to the cell as the last addition. The signal from the indicator and the reference electrode was fed to a Elico-strip chart recorder and the trace was recorded.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to D.S.T., New Delhi for supporting this work and also to Prof. B. K. Prabhakar, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga for facilities.

References

1. M. Rachwalska and A. L. Kawczynski *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 1999, **103**, 3455; L. Adamcikova, Z. Farbulova and P. Sevcik, *New J. Chem.*, 2001, **25**, 487; I. Berenstein, J. Agreda and D. Barragan, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 1999, **1**, 4601; S. B. Jonnaladadda and M. A. Salem, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 1999, **1**, 821; R. P. Rastogi, V. Syal and G. P. Misra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 203; R. P. Rastogi and S. Srivastava, *Chem., Phys. Lett.*, 1989, **164**, 173; S. Biswas, K. Mukherjee, D. C. Mukherjee and S. P. Moulik, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2001, **105**, 8857; Z. U. Nagy and I. Zimanyi, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1986, **31**, 249; V. K. Gupta and K. Srinivasulu, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1984, **24**, 235; S. C. Pal and R. S. Banerjee, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1998, **37**, 550; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 659; R. P. Rastogi, K. Mani and G. P. Misra, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1991, **178**, 171.
2. P. N. Jha, B. N. Prasad and R. K. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 177
3. S. C. Pal and R. S. Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 137; S. S. Jacobs and I. R. Epstein, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 1721.

Note

4. S. M. Pastapur and V. R. Kulkarni, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A.* 1991, **30**, 483.
5. K. J. Ladlier, "Chemical Kinetics", McGraw-Hill, Inc., New York, 1988.
6. S. M. Pastapur and V. R. Kulkarni, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 293.
7. V. R. Kulkarni, C. Basavaraja and T. K. Vishnuvardhan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 100.
8. S. M. Pastapur and V. R. Kulkarni, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A.* 1992, **31**, 183.